

How to write a Scientific Manuscript

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Levels of Editing

1. Big Picture – Audience, Style, Tone, Argument

- a. **Audience:** Who are they? What are their values, expectations, needs?
- b. **Style:** Characteristics of the writing. Expression of attitude. Complexity of sentence and diction. Ensures consistency (i.e., no changes in voice, perspective, tense).
- c. **Tone:** Author's attitude towards the subject. Found in the details (e.g., events, situations, vocabulary choice). Ensures consistency.
- d. **Argument:** The point the author is trying to get across. Promise the ending, go in order, clearly mark the pieces, and stick to the landing.

2. Containers – Paragraph Organization, Flow, Transitions, Logic, Redundancy

Paragraph Organization:

- i. Each paragraph is a container of information. Your topic sentence is the container label. Think of the transition between paragraphs as how you would organize the containers in your pantry.

Flow:

- i. Coherence (global flow) – ideas are sequenced logically at higher levels. Readers move easily from one major idea to the next without confusing jumps. Readers can follow organization and understand how the ideas are connected.
- ii. Cohesion (local flow) – Ideas are connected clearly at the sentence level with clear connections between sentences.
- iii. Know-to-new sequencing – Readers process familiar (“known”) information more quickly. More familiar information at the beginning of sentences allows readers to concentrate attention on new information in later parts.

Transitions:

- iv. Transitional expressions – Indicates the logical relationship between ideas. Ex: similarly, addition, contrast, cause and effect.

Logic:

- v. Parallel structure – Same grammatical structure for sets. Ex: Walking, talking, and chewing.
- vi. Getting to the verb – Changing the verb to a noun leads to excessively long subjects, pushing the action very far away from the beginning of the sentence. Too many words before the verb results in an unclear connection between the subject and verb.

3. Nuts and Bolts - Clarity, Redundancy, Logic, Wordiness, Verbs

Wordiness:

- vii. Filler words – words that don't add to the meaning of the sentence.
- viii. Remove wordy constructions
 1. Qualifiers – removing some will allow for a stronger, more direct point. Some are necessary but should be used carefully and thoughtfully. Ex: very, often, hopefully, practically, really, basically.
 2. Overused prepositional phrases – Little words like in, over, of, for, at, etc.

3. Stock phrases you can replace with 1 or 2 words – Phrases like “the reason for,” “for this reason,” and “due to the fact” can be changed to “because,” “since,” and “why.”

Verbs:

- ix. Passive voice – When the actor is hidden somewhere behind the action rather than the usual subject part of the sentence. Ex: The car was wrecked.
- x. Use active voice! Ex: I wrecked the car.
 - 1. Tips: Locate passive voice by finding “to be” verbs. If the “to be” verb is sitting next to another verb (especially one that ends in “ed” (or “was lost” or “was wrecked”) it may be passive.
- xi. Weak verbs – Remove verbs that lack meaning or directness.
- xii. Pronouns - Must have clear antecedents, “the patient who” never, “the patient that.” Be careful beginning a sentence with “this”. Find a summary noun: “this choice,” “this idea,” or “this allele.”

General Tips

- Know your audience to get a sense of how technical you should write.
- The first sentence of each paragraph (i.e., the topic sentence) is a clear segue into what is contained in that paragraph. See [Paragraph Organization](#).
- Each paragraph transitions smoothly from the previous paragraph and into the subsequent paragraph. See [Flow](#).
- Every *paragraph* moves the story forward, without detours. See [Flow](#); *coherence*.
- Every *sentence* moves the story forward, without detours. See [Flow](#); *cohesion*.
- Transition words (e.g., however, furthermore, subsequently, etc.) are used to guide the reader through the story. Ensure they are not overused. See [Transitions](#) and [Wordiness](#).
- Shorter sentences are used for key points. See [Wordiness](#).
- Nouns and verbs are kept together and not separated by long phrases. See [Logic](#).
- The main point is not buried at the end of a complex statement. See [Logic](#).
- Use active language. See [Verbs](#).
- Abbreviations
 - Define the first time they are used in the text, and again in all figure and table legends.
 - Note – keep number of Abbreviations minimized to avoid jargon overload.

Title

The title defines the contents of your manuscripts in as few words as possible. It has several key goals:

- Bring your manuscript to the readers' attention.
- To identify the main topic or point of your paper.

4-steps to help you create a title

Step 1: Answer key questions about your research with one-sentence answers

- What does your paper seek to answer and what does it accomplish?
- Ask questions like:
 - What is my paper about?
 - What methods/techniques did I use to perform my study?
 - What or who was the subject of my study?
 - What did I find?

Step 2: Identify research study keywords

- Take your one-sentence answers from Step 1 and identify the keywords or phrases for each answer.

Step 3: Use these keywords to create one title sentence

- This will be a complete sentence and will be much too long for your actual title.

Step 4: Create a working research paper title

- Take your sentence from Step 3, remove elements that make it a complete sentence and only keep what is important.
- Delete all unnecessary and redundant words that are not central to the study or that researchers would most likely not use in a database search.
 - This includes the number of patients studied, exact outcomes, methods used, etc.
- Shift the words for proper syntax and rephrase to shorten length.

Tips:

- Write the title after you've written your paper and abstract.
- Be concise, accurate, and informative (aim for 10-15 words unless otherwise indicated).
- Incorporate 1-2 keywords.
- Be understandable to a reader outside its field.
- Makes the primary aim of the study clear, get straight to the point.
- May incorporate the conclusion in the title.
- Does not contain abbreviations, jargon, formulae, or numbers.
- Keep away from using "Investigation of...", "Study of...", "More about...", "...revisited."
- Titles should have 3 elements: keywords, emphasis, and impact.
- Remove nonessential information and cut unnecessary words.
- Never include a period at the end of your title.

Abstract

The abstract is a short summary of your research paper. Search engines and bibliographic databases use abstracts, to identify key terms for indexing your published paper. It has several key goals:

- Readers get the gist or essence of your article quickly, in order to decide whether to read the full paper
- Prepares readers to follow the detailed information, analyses, and arguments.
- Helps readers remember the key points/takeaways from your paper.

5-steps to help you write your abstract

Step 1: Start with a background or introduction; what is currently known?

- A brief, 2 - 3 sentence introduction to the research area.

Step 2: Objectives or aims; what is the study and why did you do it?

- Clearly state the research question you're trying to answer.

Step 3: Methods; what did you do?

- Explain what you did and how you did it.
- Include important information, but avoid the low-level specifics.
- Some disciplines have specific requirements for abstract methods
 - CONSORT for randomized trials.
 - STROBE for observational studies.
 - PRISMA for systemic reviews and meta-analyses.

Step 4: Results; what did you find?

- Briefly give key findings.
- Include key numeric data (including confidence intervals or p values, if applicable).

Step 5: Conclusions; what did you conclude?

- Tell the reader why your findings matter.
- What could this mean for the 'bigger picture' of your research area?

Tips:

- A concise summary that makes sense on its own.
 - Self-contained, without abbreviations, footnotes, or incomplete references.
- Include keywords throughout.
- Avoid technical terms or background information that may not be understood without further explanation.
- Focus on key results, conclusions and take-home messages.
- Write the paper first, then create your abstract.
- Check journal requirements before you write your abstract.

Introduction

The introduction is where you set up your topic and approach for the reader. It has several key goals:

- Provide background or summarize existing research
- Position your own approach
- Detail your specific research problem and problem statement

5-steps to help you write your introduction

Step 1: Introduce your topic

- Tell the reader what your topic is and why it's interesting or important.
- Need a strong opening hook.
 - Interesting fact or statistic, a strong statement, a question, or a brief anecdote.
 - Does not need to be deeply impressive or creative. Clarity and relevance is more important.

Step 2: Describe the background

- Argumentative paper: background information.
- Empirical paper: describe previous research and establish how yours fits in.
- *Only include what is relevant to understand the study*, not a comprehensive overview.

Step 3: Establish your research problem

- Argumentative paper: emphasize importance
- Empirical paper: relate it to the literature
 - What research gap is your work intended to fill? What limitations in previous work does it address? What contribution to knowledge does it make?

Step 4: Specify your objective(s)/research aims

- Argumentative paper: thesis statement
 - Expresses the position that the rest of the paper will present evidence and arguments for. It can be presented in 1 or 2 sentences. It should state your opinion clearly and directly, without providing specific arguments for it.
- Empirical paper: research question and hypotheses
 - Presented clearly and directly, with minimum discussion.
 - Framed directly (e.g., "this study set out to...") or indirectly (e.g., "We investigated...").

Step 5: Map out your paper

- The final part is often dedicated to a brief overview of the rest of the paper.
- Concise, direct, and written in the present tense (e.g., "this paper will discuss...")

Tips:

- Only include relevant references.
- Organize the structure of your introduction section from broad to narrow.
- Use a past tense when describing the research question, problem, or hypothesis.
- Try to keep the length of this section not more than 4 paragraphs or 10-15% of the total manuscript (excluding abstract and references).

Materials and Methods

The materials and methods are where you describe how you did your research and detail the experimental procedure. This will vary in structure for each manuscript, but it has one key goal:

- Have enough detail so other researchers can replicate your experiments and reproduce your results.

6-steps to help you write your materials and methods (for medical research papers)

Step 1: Study design

- Randomized trial, observational study, prospective study, or a retrospective study. Was it double-blinded or single-blinded.

Step 2: Ethical approval

- How was ethical approval obtained for the study and clarify if the clinical trial was registered (include registration number).

Step 3: Recruitment

- How participants were recruited for study, this can include the inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Step 4: Participant grouping

- How participants were grouped into control and placebo groups, how medication was administered.

Step 5: Outcomes and follow ups

- Mention outcomes that are measured. What are the primary and secondary outcomes? What was the follow up period?

Step 6: Statistical analysis

- What tests did you use to analyze the data.
- Give as much information about the tests as possible; just mentioning a t-test is not sufficient for the reader to determine if the correct statistical analysis was performed.

Tips:

- Describe all steps chronologically and in a logical order
 - subjects/cells -> interventions -> assays -> statistical analyses
- Use subheadings (e.g., field work, lab analysis, statistical models) to guide the reader.
- Write in past tense.
- Quantify measurements.
- Don't include results.
- New methods are described in detail
- Include citations for procedures/methods/protocols that have been described previously.
 - Ensure you describe any modifications made in your project.
- Supplemental tables are used for lists of things like primer sequences or polymorphisms
- Reagents such as antibodies, cell lines, and kits are described including commercial source or donor as relevant
- Avoid discussing the pros and cons of certain methods.

Results

The results are where you report findings of your study in connection with your research question. It has several key goals:

- Summarize and present the findings of the study; only state facts and share data.
- Present the facts in an academic and unbiased manner, avoiding any attempt at analyzing or interpreting the data.

3-steps to help you write your results

Step 1: Introduction

- Connect results back to the research question.

Step 2: Present findings in a structured way

- Describe all steps chronologically and in a logical order
- Bring attention to any important, interesting, or significant findings.
 - Report actual values along with measures of variability (e.g., mean with SD, median with range, proportion with 95% confidence interval) and P values, if applicable.
 - Qualitative research – focus on descriptive and interpretive approaches.
 - Quantitative research – focus on numbers-based approaches that involve statistics, calculations, and data measurements.
- Addresses all aims and all data collected, as described in the Methods.
- Include a combination of text and visuals.
 - Data illustrations should not be used to substitute or replace text, but to enhance the narrative of your findings.
 - Uses tables for demographic data and large numerical data sets.
 - Uses figures for key outcomes related to the aims.

Step 3: Closing

- Include a closing paragraph that clearly summarizes the key findings.

Tips:

- Provide clear topic sentences that connect your findings to your research question.
- Take time to establish key findings in connection to your research question.
- Include negative or non-significant findings.
- Don't use vague terms or generalizations.
- Don't present raw data that can be summarized or presented visually.
- Don't present data that is not relevant to your research question(s).
- Uses subheadings to guide the reader, consistent to those in your methods.
- Ensure figure and table legends have enough detail to be understood independent of the narrative text
- Use supplemental materials for outcomes not directly related to the aims.
- Uses signpost phrases to guide the reader through the results (first; we next evaluated; as expected; surprisingly ...)
- Limits use of "data not shown" to information that can be readily shared with reviewers

Discussion

The discussion serves as a critical platform for researchers to interpret and connect their findings with the broader scientific context. It has several key goals:

- Conclude what your study results actually mean.
- Highlight implications while not overstating your findings.
- Compare your results to your initial hypotheses.

6-steps to help you write your discussion

Step 1: Introduction - mention gaps in previous research

- Reorient readers to study and mention the research gap your paper addresses.

Step 2: Summarize key findings - let your data speak

- Mention key findings and highlight key data and evidence supporting these findings.

Step 3: Interpreting results - compare with other papers

- Analyze and interpret any results concerning the research question or hypotheses.
 - How do the key findings of your study help verify or disprove the hypothesis?
 - What practical relevance does your discovery have?
- Can consider alternative interpretations.

Step 4: Addressing limitations – their potential impact on the results

- Discuss the potential impact of limitations on results.
 - This could include low sample size, suspected interference or noise in data, low effect size, etc.

Step 5: Implications for future research – how to explore further

- Locate areas of your research where more investigation is needed.
- Concluding paragraphs of the discussion can explain what research will likely confirm your results or identify knowledge gap your study left unaddressed.

Step 6: Conclusion – summarize content

- Revisit the research question and end by expressing the main findings of your study.

Tips:

- Present in a logical order.
 - Typically reflect order of research aims, similar to the result section.
 - Can also be re-ordered to start or finish with most interesting finding(s)
- Does not contain extraneous pathophysiology or conjecture.
- Does not contain any new results.
- Does not make statements that are not supported by the data.

Conclusions

The conclusion is where you wrap up your ideas and leave the readers with a strong final impression. It has several key goals:

- Restate the problem statement addressed in the paper.
- Summarize your overall arguments or findings.
- Suggest the key takeaways from your paper.

3-steps to help you write your conclusion

Step 1: Restate the problem

- Remind readers of your research problem, zooming out to the bigger picture.
- Avoid phrasing it identically to how it appeared in the introduction.
- Avoid starting your conclusion with phrases like “In conclusion” or “To conclude.”

Step 2: Sum up the paper

- Summarize how the paper addressed the problem and what conclusions this led to.
- Argumentative paper: restate your thesis and arguments
 - Briefly summarize the key arguments and show how each contributes to proving your thesis.
 - Mention any counterarguments you addressed, emphasizing why your thesis holds up against them, particularly if your argument is a controversial one.
 - Don't go into details of your evidence or present new ideas; focus on outlining in broad strokes.
- Empirical paper: summarize your findings
 - Don't go into great detail, but clearly express the answers to your research questions even if they were unexpected or not what you hoped for.
 - Explain the overall conclusion they led you to.

Step 3: Discuss the implications

- Consider the broader implications of your research.
 - Express the key takeaways, practice or theoretical, calls to actions or suggestions for future research.
- Argumentative paper: strong closing statement
 - Call for action; what action do you think should be taken by people or the organizations concerned in response to your argument?
 - If the topic is more theoretical and unsuitable for a call of action, this could instead express the significance of your argument (e.g., proposing a new understanding of a topic or laying the groundwork for future research).
- Empirical paper: future research directions
 - Make either recommendations for practice (e.g., in clinical or policy papers) or suggest directions for future research.
 - Finish on a forward-looking note by suggesting how you or other researchers might build on this topic in the future.
 - Address any limitations of the current paper.

